

Symptom Annotation Made Simple with SAMS

Standardized symptom capture („deep phenotyping“) allows for faster diagnosis and better research in rare diseases

SAMS Enter phenotype (Patient test_Lupus 2 ♀) testtest [Help](#)

Joint pain 2026-05-05 HPO Orphanet OMIM MAxO KBC DIMDI genes

5 results

▼ **HPO** HPO

Term	Synonyms	ID
<input type="checkbox"/> Pain		HP:0012531
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arthralgia	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Arthritic painJoint painJoint pains	HP:0002829
<input type="checkbox"/> Arthralgia/arthritis	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Joint pain/Joint inflammation	HP:0005059
<input type="checkbox"/> Arthralgia of the hip	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Hip joint painCoxalgiaHip arthralgia	HP:0003365
<input type="checkbox"/> Arthralgia/arthritis	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Joint pain/Joint inflammation	HP:0005059

Patient: test_Lupus 2 ♀

Previous visits: 2 [View](#)

Last visit: 2025-07-14 [Copy last visit](#)

[Pre-defined questionnaires.](#)

Selection

- Abdominal pain HPO [Add modifiers](#)
- Alopecia HPO [Add modifiers](#)
- Arthralgia HPO [Add modifiers](#)
- Asthenia HPO [Add modifiers](#)

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